

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

Roane State provides a cheery display for the Holiday Season.

Note the red giant star at top.

Table of Contents

Ab initio

<i>Page Three Astronomy: “Festival of the Winter Solstice”</i>	3
<i>About ORION and TRAPEZIUM</i>	4
<i>Messages from ORION</i>	
<i>President’s Message - Don Spong</i>	6
<i>TAO Director’s Message / Observatory Way - David Fields</i>	8
<i>ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito - Rob Fowler</i>	17
<i>ORION Monthly Meetings</i>	
<i>ORION Monthly Meeting Format</i>	28
<i>ORION Meeting 12 Dec 2025: Festival of the Winter Solstice and Christmas Dinner</i>	29
<i>ORION Last Month: Lunar Impact Flash Project - Richard Piety</i>	30
<i>Events and Calendars, Sky Maps and Observing Sessions</i>	
<i>Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025</i>	35
<i>TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025</i>	36
<i>Public Stargazes in Nov & Dec 2025; TAO Calendars</i>	37
<i>Public Stargaze of 15 Nov 2025 - Ted Barnes</i>	43
<i>Two occultations in one night: 1234 Elyna and 1695 Walbeck (Sun 23 Nov 2025) - Ted Barnes and Richard Piety</i>	45
<i>Public Stargaze of 06 Dec 2025 - Ted Barnes</i>	65
<i>The Evening Sky Map / Dec 2025</i>	69
<i>Astrophotography</i>	
<i>Lunar Maria - Noah Frere</i>	72
<i>Reflection Nebula IC 5076 in Cygnus - Don Spong</i>	73
<i>Appendices</i>	
<i>Astronumerology</i>	75
<i>The 80 Brightest Stars</i>	77
<i>Notable Star-Pair Angles</i>	78
<i>Exeunt</i>	
<i>Poetica</i>	80
<i>ORION and TAO General Information (and links)</i>	81
<i>Trapezium back issues online</i>	82
<i>Fin du Journal</i>	84

3rd Annual ORION FESTIVAL of the WINTER SOLSTICE & Christmas Dinner

Hello ATTENDEES

This is a quick reminder of what is planned, what is needed, and how you might contribute if desired.

First, please advise us if you plan to attend, and how many will likely be in your party, so we can make the appropriate arrangements.

The dinner will be on Friday 12 Dec 2025, at the High Places Community Church, Grove Center in Oak Ridge, with setup from 6:00 pm, and dining to begin soon afterwards.

We would appreciate people signing up to bring main dishes to be shared, as well as side dishes such as salads, veggies, pastry, dinner rolls, etc.

Serving utensils will also be appreciated.

We will provide “picnic style” plates, cutlery and napkins, but we encourage people to bring their own settings if they wish to enjoy a more festive experience.

Signup link: <https://www.perfectpotluck.com/meals.php?t=RGLT4470>

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Secretary, IT: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor: Ted Barnes

ORION Speaker POC: Richard Piety

Member w/o Portfolio: Art Allison

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we have attempted to produce a somewhat shorter version of the Trapezium, which would still include important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, as well as information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO. The information removed includes a list of the brighter active supernovae, an observers' equipment section, and personal "Meet ORION" mini-biographies. However we concluded that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them. So, the new Trapezium is only somewhat shorter, by about 20 pages.

Messages from ORION

President's Message

- Don Spong

We are approaching the Winter Solstice, occurring at UTC 15:03 on December 21. Days will gradually start becoming longer after this, so it's good to take advantage of our long nighttime viewing hours this month while they last. This month we have our 3rd Annual Orion Festival of the Winter Solstice and Christmas Dinner on Friday, December 12 (described in more detail later). We've had several successful stargazes at Tamke-Allan. Also amazing work continues to come out of our occultation efforts – see the article by Ted Barnes and Richard Piety later in this issue. I would finally add that I have recently acquired a new telescope (a 130mm Stellarvue refractor), so expect some cloudy weather; sorry about that!

December 4 was the full moon (known as the Cold Moon) and the new moon will be on December 20, with December 20-21 a good dark sky weekend. A variety of planets are now visible, including Neptune, Saturn, Jupiter and Uranus. December meteor showers include the Geminids early in the morning of December 14, the Ursids on December 21, and the Quadrantids on December 31. Comets include the mysterious 3I/Atlas (magnitude 10.8) visible in the early morning, and C/2025 T1 Atlas (magnitude 9.6) visible in early evening twilight. A variety of deep space objects are in good viewing position for December. Starting first with the star clusters, we have: M45 (the Pleiades) in Taurus, M38 (Starfish) in Auriga, M37 (Salt and Pepper) in Auriga, M36 (Pinwheel) in Auriga, the Hyades in Taurus, the double cluster NGC 869 and NGC 884 in Perseus, and M103 in Cassiopeia. Nebulas include: M42 (Orion Nebula) in Orion, NGC 2237 / C49 (the Rosette Nebula) in Monoceros, IC 410/ NGC 1893 (Tadpole) in Auriga, IC 1848 / IC 1805 (Soul/Heart) in Cassiopeia, NGC 1499 (California) in Perseus, M76 (Little Dumbbell) in Perseus, NGC 7293 (Helix) in Aquarius, and M1 (Crab) in Taurus.

President's Message (cont.)

Galaxies include: M31 (Andromeda) in Andromeda, NGC 891 / C23 (Outer Limits) in Andromeda, M33 (Pinwheel) in Triangulum, NGC 253 (Silver Dollar) in Sculptor, M77 (Cetus A) in Cetus, NGC 1300 (barred spiral) in Eridanus, NGC 1232 (spiral), also in Eridanus, and M74 (spiral), the Phantom Galaxy in Pisces. So with all of these great choices (+ maybe a few occultations), we invite you out to observe!

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way :

David Fields

December 2025

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for Roane State's Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO). Traveling West on Caney Creek Road from Roane County Park, the sign appears on the left just after crossing Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Public Stargazes and Special Events

TAO offers Public Stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month, weather permitting. From mid-October through the winter, we open by 7:30 pm and continue nominally until 10:30 pm (or later when the sky and attendance encourage this). Opening time changes according to the season, and a good guide is to arrive at the observatory about sunset, when the weather is encouraging. Our stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community. Our TAO stargazes are usually well-attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures.

December – our busiest month

The sun has lately been active with major sunspot activity. We've observed several aurorae from TAO and anticipate arrival of a coronal mass from the sun, perhaps on Dec. 9.

We're building up from a very active year of observing "asteroid occultations," with an observing event planned for lunar flashes (weather permitting) on the night of (or perhaps three successive nights starting with) Dec. 11/12.

Our annual event, this year it being the ORION 2025 Festival of the Winter Solstice and Christmas Party, on the evening of Friday Dec. 12. (See pp.3 and 34.) Don't miss it!

Observatory Way (cont.)

Aurorae Expected?

The sun has lately been active this year, with major sunspot activity. We've observed several aurorae from TAO, and anticipate the arrival of a (thin, gaseous, ionic) coronal mass from the sun, perhaps on the evening of Dec. 9.

My photo of the sun (at right), taken at the International Friendship Bell on Nov. 5, shows some interesting sunspots.

One month after the early November solar event, a new solar event (on Dec. 6), looks possibly more consequential. The above photo (from Space weather.com) shows the scale compared to the sun:

EARTH-DIRECTED SOLAR FLARE AND CME: It was *almost* an X-flare. On Dec. 6th (20:39 UTC), sunspot 4299 produced an M8-class solar flare pointing directly at Earth:

Observatory Way (cont.)

Why might we expect arrival of the expected coronal mass on Dec. 9? That's a calculated date, based on the interplanetary field (which curves the ion field) and on the velocity of the mass. My anticipation of geomagnetic events is based on predictions that arrive primarily from two sources. The left image below shows SpaceWeather (www.spaceweather.com) while on the right is the image from Astrospheric (www.astrospheric.com).

These images show the SpaceWeather and Astrospheric predictions. They predict the arrival of a CME might happen on Dec. 9, about 6 pm. Notice the Kp value on the Astrospheric chart, just below the weather pattern.

Of greater interest is [the CME](#). Both NOAA and SOHO coronagraphs detected a full halo storm cloud heading directly for Earth. NASA and NOAA models agree that the CME will arrive **Dec. 9th**:

I have several aurora apps on my phone. For spaceweather on my phone, I tested but don't recommend the "SpaceWeatherLive" iPhone app, since the ads are intrusive and a security risk. The "AuroraNotifier" iPhone app appears very useful for both aurorae and spaceweather. The AuroraNotifier prediction is shown at right.

Observatory Way (cont.)

Lunar Impact Flashes

This is a new project, mostly headed by Richard Piety. He discussed the project, being pursued with cooperation at the European Space Agency, at the November ORION meeting.

Richard's presentation was greatly appreciated, and here he receives a "thank you" from ORION treasurer Bob Edwards.

Richard and David Fields visited the SMAS group recently and discussed activities at TAO. Several SMAS folks were interested in the Lunar Impact Flash project.

Observatory Way (cont.)

November Asteroid Occultations from TAO

We've enjoyed a very active year of observing "asteroid occultations", with another observing event planned (for lunar flashes, weather permitting) on the night of Dec. 11. Hopefully everyone will have recovered and be ready for our Festival on the evening of Dec. 12.

Richard Piety observed an asteroid occultation in late November, and Ted Barnes noticed that the data looked unusual. He was able to show that the data recorded by Richard contained enough information to show the size of the red giant star being observed. (See their article in this issue.)

This Hertzsprung-Russel diagram suggests that red giants are large, but it doesn't indicate just how large. The star observed by Richard is far larger than our Sun, and if it were at the Sun's position, it would likely have absorbed Mercury.

Observatory Way (cont.)

Other Aurora of the year? How many thus far?

This year is already the best for aurora observations from TAO that we have ever seen.

The aurorae of Nov. 11-13 were beautiful, and exciting for observers across the United States. I received several messages and photos. Probably the most exciting story was from ORION member and RSCC Astronomy Student Paige Beaubain.

That photo was the start of a 3h period of Aurora observations for Paige, and part of a 2-day period of high geomagnetic activity for the planet. Paige took more astrophotos of the aurora, and I'll show two of them.

Her first photo (top right) shows the starry background, while in the foreground is a lot of horizontal structure of the aurora. Probably this is "auroral curtains" although they are not nearly as nice as one might find in Alaska.

Her second photo (left) showed the high-altitude red emission of atomic oxygen, together with the low-altitude green emission from molecular oxygen emission. The green emission is seen when the charged particles have higher energy and reach lower altitudes to encounter molecular oxygen, when the emission region is closer to the observer, and when lower light pollution permits us to see the wonderful display.

Observatory Way (cont.)

The green light emitted by molecular oxygen is clearly evident in images captured by Lynn Carter, who posted three of her aurora photos to ORIONastronomy. Her photo below shows the extensive green light emitted in this aurora, and is an especially nice example of a low-altitude green auroral display.

Observatory Way (cont.)

International Friendship Bell (IFB) Stargazes – where to setup telescopes?

We had a great daytime IFB stargaze last month. The students much enjoyed the historical and astronomical discussions that finished with examination of the bell and opportunities to ring it with the striker.

So, what is missing in the photo? The answer is “solar telescopes”. My small Seestar is shown at the right in the photo (above) but Rob’s impressive Dobsonian scope (shown here on the right) was several hundred feet away. It’s difficult to carry the larger scopes from that parking lot to the bell.

Observatory Way (cont.)

International Friendship Bell (IFB) Stargazes – where to setup telescopes?

In the future, we'll try to set up the larger scopes in a closer parking lot, located just to the South of the bell. It's a short walk across the bridge up to the telescope lot, so I hope that this is more convenient for the astronomers with larger telescopes.

Finally: ... Don't miss our Festival! (see pp.3 and 29.)

**3rd Annual ORION
FESTIVAL of the
WINTER SOLSTICE
& Christmas Dinner**

Hello ATTENDEES

This is a quick reminder of what is planned, what is needed, and how you might contribute if desired.

First, please advise us if you plan to attend, and how many will likely be in your party, so we can make the appropriate arrangements.

The dinner will be on **Friday 12 Dec 2025**, at the **High Places Community Church, Grove Center in Oak Ridge**, with setup from **6:00 pm**, and dining to begin soon afterwards.

We would appreciate people signing up to bring main dishes to be shared, as well as side dishes such as salads, veggies, pastry, dinner rolls, etc. Serving utensils will also be appreciated.

We will provide "picnic style" plates, cutlery and napkins, but we encourage people to bring their own settings if they wish to enjoy a more festive experience.

Signup link: <https://www.perfectpotluck.com/meals.php?t=RGLT4470>

FESTIVAL of the WINTER SOLSTICE & Christmas Dinner

[Meal Planning](#) [Recipes](#) [Send Them A Meal](#) [Newsletter](#) [Help](#) [Contact Us](#)

You're Invited! **ORION Festival of the 2025 Winter Solstice and Christmas** (Fri, December 12, 2025 ... 6 pm, eat soon)

Meal Coordinator: [The ORION Board](#) 865 498 9319

Meal Location: [Historic Grove Theater \(High Places Community Church\), Grove Center, Oak Ridge, TN 37830](#) [\[view map\]](#)

Notes from the ORION Board ...

ORION's FESTIVAL of the WINTER SOLSTICE and Christmas Dinner will be a potluck: Opening at 6pm, dine soon after!

We encourage attendees to wear something in the spirit of the holidays. We invite you to bring your own utensils, cups, plates and napkins. Please review the food items list at the link below, and choose something you would like to bring to share with the group. Choose whatever appears needed, and fills in the gaps.

If you bring additional friends and family members, please list another item or items that you plan to bring. (Perhaps something for each attendee.)

6:00 pm: Arrive and set up
6:30 pm: Start of the dinner
8:30 pm: Cleanup; let's leave it beautiful for the next celebration.

We hope to see you at the Historic Grove Theater on Friday Dec.12 evening!

Signup link: <https://www.perfectpotluck.com/meals.php?t=RGLT4470>

ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito

- Rob Fowler

This is a summary of topics discussed recently at the weekly (Monday 1 pm) ORION Board Meeting held as a regular working lunch at ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge. Notes as contributed in Stardate format by Sec. Rob Fowler.

Stardate: 2025.03.31

In attendance were Robert Fowler, Ted Barnes, David Fields, Art Alison and Don Spong. Discussed delays on new dome report due to committee participant availability. Discussed possible going to TAO Tuesday night. Discussed next speaker is not firm for April's meeting. Discussed voting for officers at the next ORION Meeting. Discussed the next Friendship Stargaze and date for same, 8th possibly. Discussed possibly coming up with cloudy night entertainment for Friendship stargaze. Discussed Wordsworth poem about telescopes. Discussed potential security cams for TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.07

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed the data acquired from his Arduino/LED test. David discussed a mount having the ability to track asteroids via PHD2. David discussed the Friendship Stargaze is 7:30pm Tuesday. Discussed needing pics of new concrete pads at TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted discussed results of the 785 Zwetana occultation. After a long and dramatic story, Ted revealed a successful capture. Noah is reaching out to Joe Baldwin about next month's presentation. Ted discussed quantum field theory using functional methods.

Stardate: 2025.04.21

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Noah Frere and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed how to use AnyDesk and log in unattended. Ted discussed a planetary occultation, Mars vs a 9th magnitude star on May 6th at 1 am. David discussed progress he is making with a Meshtastic receiver. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson. David brought up calendar access. Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axles. One axle migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.04.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Kevin Wilson, John Cliff and Rob Fowler. Briefly mentioned domes on CloudyNights.com. Ted discussed upcoming Mars/Star occultation and relevant challenges. HD 74058 vs Mars just after midnight 00:44 night 5th/6th morn. TAO Stargaze beginning at May 3rd 8pm. Friendship Stargaze possibly May 6th. Briefly discussed avoiding Feynman's van. Shared astrophotos. Discussed potentially going to TAO tonight & Noah's class.

Stardate: 2025.05.05

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes, Kevin Wilson, and Rob Fowler. David asked if we have a set program for May. That remains unclear. Ted contacted Noah to confirm. We await a reply. Ted mentioned the next annual IOTA meeting is possibly going to be in New Mexico in Oct.

Stardate: 2025.05.12

At 11am David, Ted & Art met at the Library and made a first pass at setting up a display case for the club. Rob joined later. It was artistically done, decorated with a small telescope, some antique books, and astrophotos. Discussed whether Kevin might give the May lecture and what topics he has ready. He agreed to speak on the topic of stellar spectroscopy. Ted mentioned the next possible occultation on the early morning on 5/21/2025.

Stardate: 2025.05.19

In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Kevin brought up Benjamin Baniker as a potential lecturer. Rob announced that the most recent lecture is on YouTube.

Star Date: 2025.05.26

In attendance were Don, Dave, Art & Rob. David suggested improvements to the Meade's power supply in hopes of reducing noise, higher amperage power supply, adding ferrite cores. Dave discussed getting a construction party to begin construction on the Dob shelter. Discussed parking issues at TAO.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.02

In attendance were Don, David, Bob, Art, Juan, Kevin and Noah (and Sunny). We met early at the library to discuss the current and new display box. Discussed meeting again, tomorrow (Tuesday). David suggested Wednesday night 8:30pm as the next Friendship Stargaze. Kevin suggested meeting at TAO to look at the Meade's encoder. Noah suggested reaching out to Gareth Davis to see if he has any potential acquaintances for another lecture. Don asked about the new dome project. David responded with a tale of woe regarding the Roane purchasing project.

Stardate: 2025.06.09

In attendance were Don, David, Art and Rob (joined by John Rather). David purchased 2 coin cells for the Celestron CGM mount. He also purchased a few ferrite cores to suppress noise from the power supply. Ted expressed an interest in having help with this month's Trapezium. Discussed the new optical telescope coming online in the Atacama Desert. Briefly mentioned the library displays and Oak Ridge street lighting. Noah mentioned that Gareth Davis can give the next lecture.

Stardate: 2025.06.16

In attendance were Don, Kevin, Art and Rob. Rob showed his submission for the AMSE poster. Kevin & Don discussed PixInsight. We confirmed Kevin is speaking this month. Kevin discussed the Astronomical League and its various programs, and contests for various achievements.

Stardate: 2025.06.23

In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin and Robert. Due to crowding at the table, no notes were taken.

Stardate: 2025.06.30

In attendance were David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Don sat in for a short while. Ted & Rob discussed results of the occultation via a new process. Kevin presented a new ORION Logo. Kevin announced he will be moving out of the immediate area.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.30

David presented Kevin with a gift ORION T-Shirt. David brought up shop type measurements he intends to do on the Meade. The group went on discuss various theoretical topics. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson David brought up calendar access. Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axels. One axel migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

Stardate: 2025.07.07

In attendance were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and visitor John Rather. Conversations opened with Ted discussing digitizing the occultation substacking project. David discussed a lightstrip project and possible application in the dome. Ted collected info for this month's Trapezium. David discussed attendance at the Sat July 5 Public Star Gaze, was 12, give or take. David discussed the testing we did on the Meade and saw no alignment errors.

Stardate: 2025.07.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted shared some mathematical analysis of the recent occultation data. David brought up potential dates for the next Friendship Star Gaze. We discussed the next ORION lecture and whether to zoom it or not. We discussed possibly having a news feature at ORION lectures.

Stardate: 2025.07.21

In attendance were David, Don, Ted, Art, Rob... and guest John. Dave led the discussion with Rob's absence. Dave mentioned that Saturday night's public star gaze was successful, with around 8 visitors. We discussed the recent lecture and the unplanned move to the computer classroom. The general consensus is that it went well. Dave will be away on August 2nd, the next star gaze. Ted brought up details of participation in the Tuesday night / Wednesday morning occultation.

Stardate: 2025.07.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison and Rob Fowler. We will probably have a public star gaze at TAO on 8/2/2025, public or private depending on weather and Noah's decision. 8/12/2025 Perseid meteor shower a probable star gaze.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.07.28

Our Library display will expire soon. David will inquire if we can keep it another month or if we need to clean it out this month. If it has to come down, Ted & Rob have agreed to remove the contents.

Stardate: 2025.08.04

Present were Don, Ted, Rob, Art and guest John Rather. Ted shared his most recent results and submission to IOTA that we have been re-evaluating. Don won't be present for the August ORION meeting. We believe John Cliff is August's speaker. We discussed various lightning phenomenon We also discussed the Big Bang theory and John Rather's book.

Stardate: 2025.08.11

Present were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and guests Richard Piety and John Rather. Ted reported on some of his recent results with IOTA's python scripts and graphing. Rob reported on visiting Lily Bluff's Star Party at Wartburg, where he met Joshua, Gareth and Owen. Don told us of a new 16 bit color astro camera he just bought, a ZWO ASI2600MCP. John told us of an experience with a pro telescope. Richard just bought a QHY174M-GPS camera for recording timed asteroid occultations. We discussed weather regarding the Perseid meteor / stargaze, 8:30pm Tuesday, but the weather is deteriorating. There is a possible occultation on 8/23/25.

Star date: 2025.08.18

In attendance were Ted, David, Art, Rob and guests John Rather and Richard Piety. David spoke to Courtney at AMSE about our ORION display. We have been invited to keep it set up for a while longer. We discussed possibly tracking 3I/ATLAS to get a pic, having an unscheduled observation evening.

Star Date: 2025.08.25

In attendance were Dave, Ted, Richard and Rob. Ted shared the results of the recent asteroid occultation. David visited the K-25 interpretive center and described the layout. He said they are interested in us bringing a star party to that location. David noticed that one of the new pads in collecting water. Rob suggested a modified a port-a-potty as a camouflage telescope cover. Calling it "Astro-Johnny: Smelling like Roses!"

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.09.01

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison and Rob Fowler. And visitor David Allred. David Fields fixed the internet at TAO and treated several ant colonies. The skies were good from 9pm to Midnight. Discussed an upcoming eclipse in Sydney Australia in 2 years. Ted spoke to the programmer of Occult Watcher [Hristo Pavlov] who helped him troubleshoot a bug. IOTA Annual meeting is next week on zoom.

Star Date: 2025.09.08

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler, Don Spong, Art Alison and Richard Piety. We has a successful Moon-gaze at TAO last night. Ted discussed his occultation studies. He was successful with one last night Sunday 2025.09.07. Richard attempted it too but has not analyzed his results yet. We had a new guest last night, Art's friend Deirdre Akin. She joined the astro-luncheon as well.

Star Date: 2025.09.15

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Don Spong, Rob Fowler and Richard Piety.

- We discussed concerns over who is coordinating speakers going forward.
- Tentatively, we believe Gareth Davies is our September speaker.
- We discussed news about the cosmic interloper 3I/Atlas and new spectral data.

ORION Board Meeting at the ElCantarito Mexican Restaurant, Oak Ridge, Mon 22 Sep 2025. L to R: Ted Barnes, David Allred, David Fields, Richard Piety, Rob Fowler, and Gareth Davies.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.09.22

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Robert Fowler, Richard Piety and guest, David Alred. Gareth Davis, Art Allison, and Don Spong arrived later.

- Ted and Richard discussed results of a recent occultation.
- Richard caught 2 new occultations recently.
- David expressed concerns over the success of last Saturday's Stargaze. He felt distracted and so thought it did not go well. But several of us thought it went very well.
- Gareth Discussed cosmic interloper 3I/Atlas, and its tail having recently turned green.
- Richard Piety confirmed that the ORION website is badly out of date.
- To support Public Star gazes, David discussed having teams of 2 to operate the Meade.
- Gareth talked about an astrophysicist, David Butler, who has a Youtube channel.

Star Date: 2025.09.29

In attendance were Don, Ted, David, Richard, Art and Robert.

- Ted told us about his visit to New Mexico and the skies at Cloudcroft.
- David asked about an abstract for October's guest speaker, Joshua from OBED.
- We discussed possibly meeting at TAO on Wednesday or Thursday.

Star Date: 2025.10.06

In attendance were David Fields, Don Spong, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler & Art Allison.

- David suggested we create something as a giveaway to members and students. He suggested a plastic ruler to help people understand angles. He also discussed making a custom planisphere.
- We discussed using Night Sky Network to coerce dues compliance. Art took up the challenge of creating a new giveaway / print project.
- Although this month's speaker is confirmed, no details have been communicated.
- Etymology needed for the expressions "cattiewumpus" and "whackadoodle."

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.10.13

In attendance were Don Spong, Ted Barnes, David Fields, Rob Fowler and Richard Piety.

- Winter Solstice is December 21, recommending having our winter solstice party on Saturday, Dec 20th. Possible locations: High Places Church. Don also suggested El Toro, a new Mexican restaurant in Oak Ridge. There is also a Chinese buffet, Hong's Asian Bistro, near Kroger's that might be possible.
- David offered suggestions about a gift for TAO members. He showed an eclipse viewer he designed.
- We discussed problems with the Meade mount and possible solutions. We also discussed adding a guide scope.
- We discussed having a new Speaker POC and potential speaker for November. Richard volunteered to be acting Speaker POC for a while and see how it works out.

Star Date: 2025.10.20

In attendance were David, Don, Art and Rob.

- Don got a photo of Comet C/2025 R2 Swan at the recent stargaze. We had a large turnout at the star gaze because of a homeschool group. Attendance was around 30 or so.
- Rob & Ted plan to go to TAO tonight to observe a 3am occultation.
- We discussed plans for a Christmas/Solstice party. David and Don will check on the availability of 2 restaurants.
- We discussed who is the key person for each of the various ORION social media assignments.
- There is no official speaker chosen for November's meeting.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.10.27

In attendance were David Fields, Don Spong, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler and Art Allison.

- Ted shared results from the most recent asteroid occultation, asteroid Chimaera.
- Considering 12/17 for the xmas party. Don & Rob shared details of 2 locations.
- David is designing a 3d joke. It's deep.

Star Date: 2025.11.03

In attendance were Dave Fields, Don Spong and Robert Fowler.

- Discussed was the weather for a planned visit to TAO tonight. Agreed on a cut off of 4:30 pm to decide if weather permits.
- David showed a printable planesphere for a youth project.
- Don mentioned a new mini clamshell dome designed for small telescopes like the see-star. We also discussed how a See-Star is designed to be used remotely.
- Rob asked if we have a speaker for this coming lecture. No specific was forthcoming.

Star Date: 2025.11.11

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Richard Piety, Rob Fowler, Don Spong, and guest John Rather. Art joined late.

- We met at noon in deference to the "Lunar Flashes" zoom call at 3pm. Richard shared some general info about their mission.
- Richard also mentioned a potential speaker, Fred Schumacher.
- Ted bought a 2 inch moon filter to aid at public star gazes.
- Richard and David discussed the general state of our web presence. ORION Astronomy has a website & a facebook page and Tamke-Allan Obs also has a website & facebook page.
- We decided to go back to the bring your own beverage & covered dish for the xmas/solstice party. Possible dates? Sat 12/13.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.11.17

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Richard Piety, Rob Fowler and Art Allison.

- Richard spoke about the LIF project (Lunar Impact Flashes) and practicing for it. He also showed a card designed to illustrate how our vision is affected by low light.
- Art showed his mock-up of the business card sized data card.
- David talked about going to the Smokey Mountain Astronomical Society meeting at Pellissippi, and invited Richard to go and speak there.
- There was some discussion about updating the website and how to communicate last minute information.

Star Date: 2025.11.24

In attendance were Dave Fields, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler and Richard Piety.

- Richard shared results from a recent pair of recent occultations and Ted offered some interesting analysis.
- Rob shared about beginning updates to the ORION Wordpress website.
- Richard mentioned that John Cliff was a potential speaker for December and asked whether we planned to have a December meeting. David reached out to John to see if he wanted to speak in January instead. It looks as if John is a go for January, so no December lecture/meeting, except the Holiday / Solstice / Christmas party.

Star Date: 2025.12.01

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler, Art Allison and Richard Piety.

- Ted discussed the occultation by asteroid 1234Elyna and why the results were unusual.
- Rob announced that the ORION Wordpress site is progressing, and requested feedback from the board members.
- Richard discussed accessing our facebook pages and giving others admin access.
- We discussed several potential future speakers, no one in particular.
- We also discussed whether the in-town Friendship Bell star gazes should continue.

ORION Monthly Meetings

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

FESTIVAL of the WINTER SOLSTICE & Christmas Dinner

[Meal Planning](#) [Recipes](#) [Send Them A Meal](#) [Newsletter](#) [Help](#) [Contact Us](#)

You're Invited! ORION Festival of the 2025 Winter Solstice and Christmas (Fri, December 12, 2025 . . .
6 pm, eat soon)

Meal Coordinator: [The ORION Board](#) 865 498 9319

Meal Location: [Historic Grove Theater \(High Places Community Church\), Grove Center, Oak Ridge, TN 37830](#) [\[view map\]](#)

Notes from the ORION Board ...

ORION's **FESTIVAL of the WINTER SOLSTICE** and **Christmas Dinner**
will be a potluck: Opening at 6pm, dine soon after!

We encourage attendees to wear something in the spirit of the holidays. We invite you to bring your own utensils, cups, plates and napkins. Please review the food items list at the link below, and choose something you would like to bring to share with the group. Choose whatever appears needed, and fills in the gaps.

If you bring additional friends and family members, please list another item or items that you plan to bring. (Perhaps something for each attendee.)

6:00 pm: Arrive and set up

6:30 pm: Start of the dinner

8:30 pm: Cleanup; let's leave it beautiful for the next celebration.

We hope to see you at the Historic Grove Theater on Friday Dec.12 evening!

Signup link: <https://www.perfectpotluck.com/meals.php?t=RGLT4470>

ORION Last Month – 19 Nov 2025

TAO Director David Fields opens the 19 Nov 2025 ORION Monthly Meeting.

ORION Last Month (cont.)

Lunar Impact Flash Project

- *Richard Piety (host)*

Our speaker for the ORION Presentation of 19 Nov 2025 was Richard Piety, a relatively recent new member of ORION. Richard has been promoting a new Europe-based campaign (LGC, the LIF Geminid Campaign) to observe flashes from small meteoroid impacts on the lunar surface, which plans to recruit a large number of international amateur astronomers to record lunar impact flashes (LIFs) during the Geminid meteor shower, over the period 12-14 Dec 2025. Participants at TAO have already started testing their observing equipment for this new effort.

Richard Piety tells the audience about plans to observe LIFs at TAO.

ORION Last Month (cont.)

The presentation consisted primarily of a recorded Zoom talk on LIFs to likely participants by Detlef Koschny, LGC Project Director and Prof. of Engineering at the Technische Universität München (TUM). Detlef is explaining things from the insert at center right.

What do we see?

$E_{lum} \sim \mu \frac{1}{2} mv^2$ where μ : luminous efficiency
But note: μ is a function of v .

Prof. D. Koschny - AMM-HO-127, Nov 2025

001:27

STD-video1920940303 - E

TUM

$t = 0.165 \text{ s}$

01. Mar. 2017
(source: NASA/JPL/ESA)

LRO image credit:
NASA/JSC/CASU

001:27

001:27

001:27

ORION Last Month (cont.)

Richard receives his ORION Speaker's mug from Bob Edwards after the presentation.

Events and Calendars, Sky Maps and Observing Sessions

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, model 3200008, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we are reverting to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](https://groups.io/g/ORIONastronomy).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a Moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours of approximately 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm, with some nominal variation.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous page and following two pages of this issue.

TAO Public Stargazes in November: Sats 01 & 15 Nov 2025

Sat 01 Nov 2025

Sunset	6:43 pm
Civ dusk	7:10 pm
Ast dusk	8:10 pm
Moonrise	4:23 pm
Moonset*	2:31 am
	*02 Nov

Moon illum. 79%

**Waxing Gibbous Moon.
Bright Moon during this event.**

Sat 15 Nov 2025

Sunset	5:32 pm
Civ dusk	5:59 pm
Ast dusk	7:01 pm
Moonrise	2:56 am
Moonset	3:04 pm

Moon illum. 27%

**Waning Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.**

TAO Public Stargazes in December: Sat 06 & 20 Dec 2025

Sat 06 Dec 2025

Sunset	5:25 pm
Civ dusk	5:54 pm
Ast dusk	6:57 pm
Moonrise	7:10 pm
Moonset*	10:35 am
	*07 Dec

Moon illum. 96%

**Waning Gibbous Moon.
Bright Moon during this event.**

Sat 20 Dec 2025

Sunset	5:29 pm
Civ dusk	5:58 pm
Ast dusk	7:01 pm
Moonrise	8:31 am
Moonset	5:52 pm

Moon illum. 0%

**Waxing Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.**

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun & Jul-Dec 2025; Nov & Dec 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for six month periods, currently Jul-Dec 2025. These appear on the two pages immediately following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations, Meteor Showers, Full Moonrises, Lunar (and other) Eclipses, Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the two six-month “Public Stargaze” calendars.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as <http://www.roanestate.edu/obs> before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 07 Jun 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Public Stargaze

Jul-Dec 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 05 Jul 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 19 Jul 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 02 Aug 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 16 Aug 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sun 07 Sep 2025	<small>moved</small> ★	"1 st Sat" Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 20 Sep 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 04 Oct 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Oct 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Mon 03 Nov 2025	<small>moved</small> ★	"1 st Sat" Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Nov 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 06 Dec 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 20 Dec 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Special Events (all times Eastern)

Nov 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 01 Nov 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sun 02 Nov 2025		End of DST 2025		1:00 am
Wed 05 Nov 2025		Full Moon 08:19 am Eastern		
Sat 15 Nov 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Thu 20 Nov 2025		New Moon 01:47 am Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events (all times Eastern)

Dec 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Thu 04 Dec 2025		Full Moon 06:14 pm Eastern		
Sat 06 Dec 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm
Fri 12 Dec 2025		ORION Winter Solstice & Christmas Dinner Festival	6:00 pm	t.b.a.
Fri-Mon 12-15 Dec 2025		Lunar Impact Flash (LIF) Campaign	00:49 am 12 Dec 2025	06:09 am 15 Dec 2025
Fri 19 Dec 2025		New Moon 08:43 pm Eastern		

Public Stargaze of Sat 15 Nov 2025

- Ted Barnes

Sat 15 Nov 2025

Unfortunately I took only minimal notes during this stargaze. I arrived just after 7:00 pm, and we had something like a dozen visitors. Initially the sky was not especially good, so we moved the visitors inside for astronomy talks. David Fields gave his TAO overview talk, following which at 8:00 pm I gave a two-part talk on asteroids and occultations. The first part was introductory, so after that 20 mins was up I said that anyone who had enough might depart. One father and daughter left, following this the next 20 mins was a full blast talk about the recent campaign to capture group observations of the asteroid 623 Chimaera, which would allow assembly of

Sunset	6:32 pm
Civ dusk	6:59 pm
Ast dusk	8:01 pm
Moonrise	3:56 am
Moonset	4:04 pm

Moon illum. 19%

Waning Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.

Public Stargaze of Sat 15 Nov 2025 (cont.)

a profile of that asteroid. The audience stayed with me until I finished at 8:40 pm, and they did appear to enjoy the talk. At the end I had to tell them that although I had seen the profile of 623 Chimaera, release to the public was still embargoed by the collaboration, so I could only confirm that “Is potato.”

As the sky had improved by then, our visitors next enjoyed views with Rob using the Meade (Saturn and the Pleiades were available), and they also enjoyed seeing the 8” refractor. A group of visitors touring the large refractor is shown below.

Unfortunately the weather soon deteriorated, and by 9:00 pm we were faced with an overcast. Our visitors departed by about 9:30 pm.

Happy visitors hoping to find an exit from the large refractor dome.

Two Occultations in One Night: 1234 Elyna and 1695 Walbeck (Sat/Sun 22/23 Nov 2025).

- Ted Barnes and Richard Piety

Ted Barnes' section:

One learns of coming occultations observable at your chosen location(s) from the program Occult Watcher, which gives you a regularly updated list of these opportunities. The especially attractive ones tend to have long durations, bright target stars (to be occluded), and occur at times not too challenging to attend. The possibility of observing two such occultations in a single night at TAO was a very interesting opportunity when it appeared on Occult Watcher. The date of these two events would be early on the morning of Sunday 23 Nov 2025, not long after midnight, and would involve two unusually bright target stars, both of magnitude 7.9. This is brighter than any target star our group had previously observed in an occultation, which meant that fast frames could be used to record the events, with correspondingly accurate event timing. The absence of moonlight was another attractive feature of this “double-header.”

Sat 22 Nov 2025

Sunset	5:28 pm
Civ dusk	5:56 pm
Ast dusk	6:58 pm
Moonrise	9:44 am
Moonset	7:01 pm

Moon illum. 5%

Waxing Crescent Moon.

No Moon visible during this event.

1234 Elyna

The first occultation would involve the asteroid 1234 Elyna, a 26 +/- 1.6 km diameter asteroid in the outer main belt. It was predicted that this asteroid would occult the red giant TYC 600-1446-1 at a midpoint time of 00:27:48 Eastern, with a maximum predicted duration of 8.1 [sec]. This would take place in Pegasus, at Alt-Azi coords of 34°@261°, slightly to the SW of the star Algenib (γ Peg), which is the bottom left star in the great square of Pegasus (see chart, following page).

1695 Walbeck

Only five minutes later the second occultation was expected to take place, involving 1695 Walbeck, a 19.5 +/- 1 km diameter asteroid in the outer part of the middle main belt. This asteroid would occult the star TYC 156-1954-1 at a midpoint time of 00:32:52 Eastern, with a somewhat shorter maximum predicted duration of 2.0 secs. This would take place on the other side of the sky, at Alt-Azi coords of 40°@118°. This event would be in the faint constellation Monoceros, not far from the 4th magnitude, type-K0III giant star 18 Monocerotis (see chart, two pages following).

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Position of asteroid 1234 Elyna in Pegasus at the time of the occultation, 00:27:48 am Eastern, 23 Nov 2025. Image from TheSkyX.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Position of 1695 Walbeck in Monoceros at the time of the occultation, 00:32:52 am Eastern, 23 Nov 2025. Image from TheSkyX.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

To prepare for this multiple occultation I assembled the usual star charts (wide-field and telescope/camera field of view), JPL orbit diagrams, and asteroid shadow path maps, and on 20 Nov sent this material to “ORION and friends” astronomers who I thought might be interested. I had also mentioned this upcoming occultation at the monthly ORION meeting, on Wed 19 Nov.

Of course the main uncertainty, as usual, was the weather. In my 20 Nov group email I included the warning that

“weather.com says partly cloudy. but it's downhill from there.

CSC says clear 11-12 [pm], but 80% ocast 12-1 am.

astrosph says 35% ocast 11-12 [pm], and 93% ocast 12-1 [am].

ugh.

But will it change tomorrow? The predicted clouds have lots of gaps.”

The weather uncertainty was very frustrating. As the days and nights passed there was no clear consensus between weather dot com, CSC and Astrospheric about the night of 22-23 Nov. The latter of the three, to which many people tend to assign a higher level of respect, predicted a generally clear night for 22-23 Nov, but with a persistent but fluctuating few hours' knot of clouds around a crucial period of midnight to 4 pm. I began losing sleep to check the changing forecast every few hours. For a day or two beforehand the post-midnight 23 Nov knot of clouds appeared to be dispersing, but on the morning of 22 Nov it was back with renewed force, so I finally told people that I was giving up on this event, and was going to have a nap.

When I again checked online about 4 pm on the afternoon of 22 Nov there was still some interest, and Richard Piety was planning to attend. I however was just too stressed out by the fluctuating weather predictions and exhausted by my lack of sleep, so I said that I might well attend that evening, but without equipment. Richard was the only person to actually set up at TAO for the occultation, and I tried to assist by interacting with him that evening by cell phone and messages, and gave him some information he would need about the two occultations. (There were actually three, there was an earlier faint occultation about 11 pm on 22 Nov, but that one was knocked out by a badly timed cloud.) By then Astrospheric was claiming only a few percent cloud cover at TAO! Richard said there was clearly more cloud than that, but he was still able to set up for the two major occultations of *ca.* midnight:30 on Sun 23 Nov. Since he was the only person actually present at TAO that evening, I will now turn the narrative over to him.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Richard Piety's section:

I arrived at the Tamke-Allan Observatory around 9:30 PM. There was a ring of clouds around the horizon but clear overhead. I decided to take a chance and set up my Celestron C8 with Hyperstar v4 telescope and QHY174MGPS camera riding on a ZWO AM5 Mount. It was a somewhat chilly night at 45-50 degrees F and a light intermittent breeze.

I was a little apprehensive about catching two occultation 5 minutes and 144 degrees apart. As I was setting up my equipment and getting the software running. I got a message from Dr. Ted Barnes, "Hey there is a third occultation around 11 PM you might want to catch!" Well, why not? I had a few hours to wait before the main double event. Ted sent me the specifics.

Asteroid 97015 occulting star UCAC4 627-018517 turns out to be a magnitude 13.3 event lasting a mere 0.4 second max. This meant I really needed to make 50 mSec exposures to have several data points during the occultation. When I tested my set-up on the target star, 150 mSec with a gain of 450 was the best I could do and still see the star. Even at that setting, the star would occasionally fade away, likely due to a thin haze deteriorating the seeing. However, the image was holding pretty steady as the time to kick-off the capture approached. I was getting optimistic. Its time! Start capture! The star fades away for the entire 60 second acquisition. Expletive! Expletive!

Oh well, my primary targets were an hour and 20 minutes away, and they were mag 7.9. I would be able to get them, haze or not.

I began my prep for the two upcoming occultations. Asteroid 1234 Elyna occulting star TYC 600-1446-1 at 12:27 am and asteroid 1695 Walbeck occulting star SAO 114492 at 12:32 am. These occultations had a duration of 8.1 sec and 2.0 sec respectively. This would have been great at any exposure approaching 200 mSec. Except that in the dark I read 8.1 to be 0.1!

What the heck! At 0.1 sec I would need a 20 mSec or less exposure to get several data points. I tested 20 mSec at a 350 gain and had good visibility. Great! Except to get 50 frames per second (FPS) I needed to decrease the image size to 640x480. Okay, that's done, I have the star's position confirmed with a plate-solve in SharpCap, So I will move on to the next occultation and get my setup parameters confirmed for it.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

For the next occultation, 1695 Walbeck, the scope would have to swing from an azimuth of 118 degrees to a new position at 261 degrees. Once there I would need to plate-solve to center the correct target star, check my focus, change to a more sedate 100 mSec exposure for the 2.0 sec occultation, and prepare to start a new SharpCap video capture. Hopefully with no unexpected mishaps, I would do this in approximately 3 minutes and 20 seconds.

It is time! Start the capture!

00:26:48 Start 1234 video capture

00:28:48 End 1234 capture

Reposition scope, Plate-Solve, Adjust SharpCap settings, Check Focus, Set up Capture and start capture.

00:32:00 Start 1695 video capture

00:34:00 End 1695 capture.

Whew! Success! Pack up and head home. Not too bad, 4 hours invested for 4 minutes worth of data.

1234 Elyna occultation.

1695 Walbeck occultation.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Ted Barnes's section:

First we consider the occultation data for the *second* asteroid, 1695 Walbeck, with the light curve shown on the bottom right of the previous page, since this proved to be an essentially classic occultation with few complications. Richard captured this data with a moderate camera gain of 350 and rather conservative 100 ms frames (this bright target star could have supported much shorter frames; 20 ms would have been my choice). He ran this data through the IOTA analysis programs Pymovie and Pyote; the latter fits a square-well model to the occultation event. The results (with 1σ errors) were an event midpoint of 05:32:51.1995(21) UT and a duration of 1.7347(42) [sec]; note the truly excellent tiny errors of 2 ms and 4 ms respectively. As the predicted event midpoint had been 05:32:52 UT with an estimated error of 0.3 secs, this observation is an improvement over the prediction by 2 to 3 orders of magnitude. Similarly there was a maximum duration prediction of 2.0 [secs], so the observed duration is consistent, but much more precise.

Inspection of the occultation light curves shows nearly ideal transitions, with a single data point in the Reappearance phase, but two points during the Disappearance. This is evidence that the initial transition was somewhat longer than the frame length of 100 ms.

Since TAO was 12 [km] from the shadow center line and the asteroid had an estimated shadow width of 30 [km], the fractional distance of TAO from the center to the shadow's edge was $x = 12/15 = 0.8$. If we assume a circular shadow, the predicted maximum duration of 2.0 [sec] would be reduced by $\sqrt{1-x^2}$ to 1.2 [sec]. The observed duration was somewhat larger than this rough estimate, but of course an asteroid of this size may be quite irregular.

The expected magnitude drop was 16.7 (ast) – 7.9 (star) = 8.8 [mag], whereas the observed drop was 6.5 +/- 0.6 [mag]. This is about as expected; the 3σ discrepancy is likely not a problem, since the faint luminosity recorded at the bottom of the well was only about 2σ from zero.

Finally, note that Richard was the only observer of this occultation by 1695 Walbeck. But for his effort, none of these results would have been recorded and reported to IOTA.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Next we proceed to the occultation data for the *first* asteroid, **1234 Elyna**, shown enlarged below as a reminder. This is a very interesting event, with an unexpected and exciting complication.

For this event Richard again used a moderate camera gain of 350, but as he stated earlier he had accidentally used much shorter frames of 20 ms. This was quite fortunate, since it gives us much better time resolution for the event, and would actually have been my choice.

Richard again processed his data using the IOTA analysis programs Pymovie and Pyote, and the results of Pyote's square-well fit are shown below. (The target star luminosity measurements are blue; the purple points are from a slightly fainter comparison star.)

We can immediately see that the Pyote square-well model does not give a satisfactory description of this data; the assumed instantaneous disappearance (D) and reappearance (R) events are observably distributed over time. From the 20 ms blue points we can estimate that the disappearance took ~ 0.5 sec, and the reappearance was somewhat longer.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

This data suggests that the light from the target star is a distributed source rather than a point. One might attribute this to an atmospheric scattering effect, or perhaps to the finite size of the target star's disc. Since the star is of known type and distance, we can first estimate how large its disc should be. Since this asteroid was moving across the sky at an angular rate of 2.14 [mas/sec] (milliarcseconds per second), a disappearance time of about 0.5 [sec] could be explained by a light source about 1 [mas] in extent.

The Gaia data on the target star TYC 600-1446-1, *a.k.a.* SAO 91710 and Gaia EDR3 2766314085176077056, places it at a distance of 547(9) pc, with a g-mag of 7.90 and (from Simbad) a visual magnitude of 8.71, hence an absolute magnitude of +0.02, about 84 times the Sun's luminosity. Simbad gives a spectral type of M0, and in a Hertzsprung-Russell diagram these properties classify it as an M0III red giant (see following page). A typical diameter for a red giant of this type is 0.5 AU. At a distance of 0.55 kpc such a star would have an angular extent of 0.9 mas, which is essentially the angular size estimated above as corresponding to a disappearance time of 0.5 secs. Thus the "rounded" D and R light curves seen in the 1234 Elyna data on the previous page appear to be an expected consequence of the target star being an M0III red giant star at 0.5 kpc.

Let's proceed to develop a simple quantitative model of this red giant finite size effect for comparison with the Elyna data. First we assume a uniformly bright circular disc for the star. If during disappearance the asteroid has covered a fraction $(x+1)/2$ of this disc ($x = -1$ is contact, 0 is center, +1 is complete), the target star's brightness will be reduced by a multiplicative factor of

$$f_D(x) = 1/2 - (1/\pi) \left[x \sqrt{1-x^2} + \text{atan}(x/\sqrt{1-x^2}) \right] .$$

A graph of this uniform disk disappearance function is shown on the second page following.

Similarly, during a reappearance the target star's luminosity is multiplied by a factor of $f_R(x)$, which has a change of sign after the 1/2.

To fit the 1234 Elyna data we first subtract the mean value of the luminosity in the well (which the Pyote log gives as 3894) from the data, and then scale it by the Pyote fitted mean luminosity range, 222037 – 3894. This gives target star luminosity data scaled to the mean maximum outside the well, and the mean minimum inside the well, which are then respectively 1 and 0.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Position of the Elyna target star TYC 600-1446-1 in a Hertzsprung-Russell diagram.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Uniform stellar disc disappearance function

$$f_D(x) = 1 - f_R(x) = 1/2 - (1/\pi) [x \sqrt{1-x^2} + \text{atan}(x/\sqrt{1-x^2})] .$$

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

For the time axis we assume the mean frame duration found by Pyote, 0.0224365 [sec], and by definition set the time of the midpoint of the initial frame to 0.0 [sec]. According to the Pyote log the initial frame starts at 05:26:47.9857025 UT, so our working data time of 0.0 [sec] starts at that initial UT time plus 0.0224365/2.0 secs. (The latter shift moves us to the midpoint of the first frame, for working time 0.0 [sec].)

We fit the disappearance D and reappearance R regions of the 1234 Elyna data separately. Each curve has 2 parameters, the transition midpoint time t^c and the transition duration t^{dur} . Note t^c and t^{dur} only refer to the D and R events, not to the full occultation.

A least-squares fit to the Elyna disappearance data gives the D parameters $t^c = 56.690$ [sec] and $t^{\text{dur}} = 0.494$ [sec] (blue curve). A similar fit to the Elyna reappearance data gives the R parameters $t^c = 60.609$ [sec] and $t^{\text{dur}} = 0.786$ [sec] (red curve). The combined fitted curve and the scaled data are shown below. This model gives a satisfactory representation of the data for our purposes.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

These fitted parameter values give a brightness midpoint-to-midpoint duration for the full occultation of

$$\text{Event duration} = 3.918 \text{ [sec]}$$

and an occultation time midpoint of 58.650 [sec]. The occultation time midpoint in UT can be determined as described two paragraphs previously, and is

$$\text{Event midpoint} = 05:27:46.647 \text{ (UT)} .$$

This is about 1.3 [sec] before the predicted time of 05:27:48 (UT), which had a 1 [sec] estimated error.

Regarding the duration of the occultation, the predicted duration was 8.1 [sec]. Here the distance from shadow midline was 15 [km] and the shadow half-width was 23 [km], so the suppression of the occultation duration in the circular profile approximation would be $\sqrt{1-(15/23)^2} = 0.76$, giving an estimated duration of 6.1 [sec]. The observed duration of the occultation, about 3.9 [sec], is well below that simple estimate.

Of course the size of the red giant that is required to explain the observed light curve is especially interesting, but unfortunately without additional information we can only provide limits. Although we know the durations of stellar “starset” and “starrise” from fitting the target star light curves, and they are respectively 0.494 [sec] and 0.786 [sec], we will see that we also need to know the angle the star makes with the asteroid’s limb on encounter (disappearance) and departure (reappearance).

First consider the disappearance. We will initially assume that the star crosses the asteroid’s limb “normally” (meaning at a right angle to the horizon). In this case the setting time for the star’s disc, from contact to vanishing point, is given by

$$T_{\text{set}} = \Theta_{\text{star}} / \omega_{\text{ast}}$$

where the angle Θ_{star} subtended by the star’s disc (in the extremely well justified small-angle approximation) is the star’s diameter divided by the distance to the star,

$$\Theta_{\text{star}} = \text{Diam}_{\text{star}} / \text{dist}_{\text{star}} .$$

So, we find for our target star diameter estimate

$$\text{Diam}_{\text{star}} = T_{\text{set}} \omega_{\text{ast}} \text{dist}_{\text{star}} .$$

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Plugging in our “disappearance” numbers $T_{\text{set}} = 0.494$ [sec], $\omega_{\text{ast}} = 2.14$ [mas/sec] and $\text{dist}_{\text{star}} = 0.576$ [kpc], we find for our red giant target star diameter estimate

$$\text{Diam}_{\text{star}} = 0.494 \text{ [sec]} * 2.14 \text{ [mas/sec]} * 0.576 \text{ [kpc]} = 0.578 \text{ [mas kpc]}.$$

1 [mas kpc] is better known as 1 [AU] (see the Astronomerology section of this issue of the Trapezium), so this becomes

$$\text{Diam}_{\text{star}} = 0.578 \text{ [AU]}.$$

This is roughly the size expected for an M0III red giant.

Now for the complication.

The diameter estimate of 0.578 [AU] assumed that the asteroid was moving in a direction normal to its horizon. Of course in general the asteroid’s horizon will intercept the star at some other angle θ , as shown in the two diagrams on the following page. This changes the formula for the target star’s diameter:

For an initial disappearance at an oblique angle θ_D , the result for the star’s setting time becomes

$$T_{\text{set}} = \Theta_{\text{star}} / (\omega_{\text{ast}} \cos(\theta_D)) .$$

Again substituting $\Theta_{\text{star}} = \text{Diam}_{\text{star}} / \text{dist}_{\text{star}}$, we now find for the target star’s diameter

$$\text{Diam}_{\text{star}} = T_{\text{set}} \omega_{\text{ast}} \cos(\theta_D) \text{dist}_{\text{star}} .$$

Plugging in our “disappearance” numbers $T_{\text{set}} = 0.494$ [sec], $\omega_{\text{ast}} = 2.14$ [mas/sec] and $\text{dist}_{\text{star}} = 0.576$ [kpc], we find for our red giant target star diameter estimate

$$\text{Diam}_{\text{star}} = 0.578 \text{ [AU]} * \cos(\theta_D) .$$

Thus our previous estimate of 0.578 [AU] for the target star’s diameter was only an upper limit, which is saturated in the special case of normal incidence of the star’s disc relative to the asteroid’s horizon, $\theta_D = 0^\circ$.

Similar results apply to the star’s reappearance. In that case the stellar disc set time is replaced by the longer T_{rise} time of 0.786 [sec], and the stellar disc diameter is given by

$$\text{Diam}_{\text{star}} = 0.920 \text{ [AU]} * \cos(\theta_R) .$$

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Normal incidence: The time for the stellar disc to cross the asteroid's horizon is Θ/ω , where Θ is the diameter of the star's disc [mas] and ω is the angular velocity of the asteroid across the sky [mas/sec].

Oblique incidence: The time for the stellar disc to cross the asteroid's horizon is $\Theta / (\omega \cos(\theta))$, where Θ is the diameter of the star's disc [mas], ω is the angular velocity of the asteroid across the sky [mas/sec], and θ is the angle between the asteroid's motion across the sky and a normal to the asteroid's local horizon.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

These two relations for $\text{Diam}_{\text{star}}$ give us a constraint on the angles of the horizon normal to the asteroid's direction of motion in the reappearance versus disappearance transitions,

$$\cos(\theta_R) / \cos(\theta_D) = T_{\text{set}} / T_{\text{rise}} = 0.628 .$$

So, from the results of a single observer we can perhaps surprisingly extract information about the asteroid's surface angles at two locations, using this finite stellar disc model.

Since we have one constraint on the two angles θ_D and θ_R , we only know both angles if one is specified. As an example, if we know that the disappearance event takes place at normal incidence ($\theta_D = 0^\circ$, as shown on the following page), it follows that the reappearance event happens with $\theta_R = 51^\circ$. See the graph below for the general allowed solutions, given the T_{set} and T_{rise} times observed for 1234 Elyna. Note also that since \cos is an even function, the overall signs of the angles are not determined by the constraint equation above.

The relation between the incident (D) angle and the outgoing (R) angle.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Relating the incident and exit angles: In this figure the star reappears at an oblique angle θ_R relative to the local horizon, which results in a longer reappearance (R) or “rise” time than disappearance (D) or “set” time. For simplicity, a case with normal incidence ($\theta_D = 0^\circ$) is shown here. In general, $\cos(\theta_R) / \cos(\theta_D) = T_{\text{set}} / T_{\text{rise}}$.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

Although the smaller disappearance angle (θ_D in this case) is *a priori* unconstrained, $0^\circ < \theta_D < 90^\circ$, the above relation between $\cos(\theta_D)$ and $\cos(\theta_R)$ implies a constrained range of values for the reappearance angle θ_R , which for 1234 Elyna is

$$51^\circ < \theta_R < 90^\circ .$$

The lower limit is reached for the special case of $\theta_D = 0^\circ$.

A question we have not yet addressed is why the occultation by 1234 Elyna was special, in that the finite transition times observed in the disappearance and reappearance were so clearly evident in this event. To better understand this, recall for example the expression we found for the transition “set” time of the red giant star during disappearance;

$$T_{\text{set}} = \Theta_{\text{star}} / (\omega_{\text{ast}} \cos(\theta_D)) = \text{Diam}_{\text{star}} / (\text{dist}_{\text{star}} \omega_{\text{ast}} \cos(\theta_D)) .$$

How can we maximize the time T_{set} spent in the disappearance phase, allowing a more accurate investigation? Besides the obvious choices of making the star larger or closer, observing an occultation by an asteroid moving especially slowly across the sky (small ω_{ast}) will find longer, and hence better observed, target star disappearance and reappearance times.

If we consider values of ω_{ast} in recent occultations, we can see that having a small ω_{ast} is indeed important. In a set of 20 more or less randomly chosen recent or near future occultations at TAO, the occultation with 1234 Elyna had the 19th smallest rate of asteroid motion, 2.14 [mas/sec]. Typical values for the main-belt asteroids are a much faster ~ 8 [mas/sec]. Of the reasonably common types of occultation asteroids, only the Jupiter Trojans usually have much smaller values of ω_{ast} ; 1 to 4 [mas/sec] is typical in that case.

As a final illustration of the importance of having a small rate of motion across the sky, in the following figure we show the asteroid velocity ω_{ast} in milliarcsecs per sec ([mas/sec]) for 1234 Elyna and its “partner” occultation involving 1695 Walbeck for a period of +/- 50 days surrounding these two 23 Nov occultations. Evidently near the date of the occultations 1234 Elyna was accidentally in a special position in its orbit relative to Earth that gave it an exceptionally slow rate of motion in the sky. This slow motion effectively stretched the horizontal axis of the 1234 Elyna light curve by about a factor of 4 relative to the typical scale, making the rounded shape of the disappearance and reappearance transitions much more evident than would normally be the case.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

The moral is that if one wishes to select occultations that will be most useful in inferring target star diameters, one should choose events that have especially slowly moving asteroids. Of course having a bright target star is essential as well.

Two Occultations in One Night (cont.)

References and credits to materials used to produce this article are as follows:

The two skymaps showing the locations of two occultation events were generated using the program TheSkyX.

The diagram showing angular velocities on the final page was produced using data generated by the program TheSkyX.

The Hertzsprung-Russell diagram is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.5 License, as specified at the link [www dot atlasoftheuniverse dot com / copyright dot html](http://www.atlasoftheuniverse.com/copyright.html). The diagram was modified by the addition of a reference to the star TYC 600-1446-1 occulted by asteroid 1234 Elyna.

Public Stargaze of Sat 06 Dec 2025

- Ted Barnes

Sat 06 Dec 2025

These seems to have been some confusion related at TAO access times for this event. Some people such as Richard and to a lesser extent myself needed earlier access than the initially suggested 7:00 pm, in my case because I had been requested by David to start my Moon Music collection with the arrival of the nearly full moon. According to my references the Moon would reach the horizon at 7:10 pm, so I preferred to arrive earlier, perhaps 6:30 or 6:45 pm, to begin setup of my audio equipment. I missed the details of the discussion, and arrived happily about 6:30 pm just as David was opening the TAO gate. I drove down to the NE pad where Richard Piety was already setting up, and set up my lighter complement of equipment for the evening,

Sunset	5:25 pm
Civ dusk	5:54 pm
Ast dusk	6:57 pm
Moonrise	7:10 pm
Moonset*	10:35 am
	*07 Dec

Moon illum. 96%

**Waning Gibbous Moon.
Bright Moon during this event.**

Moon Music being played (from 7:10 pm) to encourage the moon to rise above the trees.

7:47 pm Eastern, 06 Dec 2025. Moon position Alt 05.15°, Azi 61.02°. Phase 93.6°.

Orion is visible at lower right.

Public Stargaze of Sat 06 Dec 2025 (cont.)

consisting mostly of lightweight audio equipment. I briefly strolled into the TAO building, where a visitor had several questions for me about relativity theory. (Several of our visitors were home schoolers, who take astronomy quite seriously. Later another asked me about Polaris not being the pole star in the future.) The earlier discussions were intricate enough that I had to be reminded that I needed to start up the Moon Music at 7:10 pm.

Just before Moonrise I remembered that I planned to test the darkness of the TAO skies with my new SQM meter. The result was 20.33 [mag/asec²] in the darkest direction (West of the zenith), ranging down to 20.2 [mag/asec²] (East of the zenith, towards Kingston). The darker value is close to 20.3 [mag/asec²], which corresponds to Bortle 5.0. Lest one be discouraged, I should note that this was at about 7:00 pm, just at the start of astronomical dusk. But for Moonrise, the sky would presumably have grown considerably darker. This will be tested in future TAO visits.

Rob (L) giving our visitors a view of the Moon near the horizon with the Meade LX-200.

7:55 pm Eastern.

Public Stargaze of Sat 06 Dec 2025 (cont.)

After some discussions outside and telescope viewing using the Meade, we assembled for astronomy lectures inside the TAO building about 8:00 pm. David Fields welcomed our guests (perhaps about 15 in total) and gave an overview of TAO and associated activities, which took about 50 mins. I had trimmed and updated my asteroids and occultations talk considerably: This Big Kitty-40 version included a basic Asteroids 101 introduction, followed by a description of the 23 Nov double occultation, our most recent TAO occultation. Total talk time about 30 mins. I told the audience about our exciting discovery that the target star for the 1234 Elyna occultation, TYC 600-1446-1, was a red giant. This meant that we could see the dimming and brightening of the target star as the asteroid gradually covered and uncovered the stellar disc. I also noted that the audience, if interested, could read more about this occultation in the Dec 2025 Trapezium (pp.45-64).

The warm audience for our TAO astronomy lectures. 8:20 pm Eastern.

Public Stargaze of Sat 06 Dec 2025 (fin.)

After the lectures ended about 8:30 pm most of our visitors returned to the outside, where the very bright Moon, with Jupiter dangling beneath like a jewel, almost gave the impression of twilight. Popular topics for both the Meade (operated by Rob) and the 8" refractor (operated by Paige and Aaron) were Jupiter and the Pleiades, and since we had a representation by home schoolers, many kiddies as well as adults were present to enjoy seeing these objects.

Gradually our visitors thinned, and then departed by about 10 pm. A last puzzle was a very bright object on the horizon to the West. Here my binoculars solved the mystery, and I announced to Richard Piety that it was a star. He was VERY skeptical, but I was right, it was a star, a giant white Christmas star several miles away, composed of artificial white lights.

The sky gradually clouded somewhat, and displayed several Moon-backlit faint diffuse contrails. After some discussions with others in the TAO building about what a pleasant night this had been, I finally departed about 11 pm. Wet surfaces had been a problem all evening (we had been near or at the dew point throughout), and while packing up just before 11 pm I noticed that the surface of my worktable had a thin layer of ice. Something to remember and plan for in the coming days and weeks of winter observing!

A bright “star” on the horizon to the West. 10:35 pm Eastern.

The evening Sky Map for December 2025 from skymaps.com.

About the Celestial Objects

Listed on this page are several of the brighter, more interesting celestial objects visible in the evening sky this month (refer to the monthly sky map). The objects are grouped into three categories. Those that can be easily seen with the naked eye (that is, without optical aid), those easily seen with binoculars, and those requiring a telescope to be appreciated. **Note, all of the objects (except single stars) will appear more impressive when viewed through a telescope or very large binoculars.** They are grouped in this way to highlight objects that can be seen using the optical equipment that may be available to the star gazer.

Tips for Observing the Night Sky

When observing the night sky, and in particular deep-sky objects such as star clusters, nebulae, and galaxies, it's always best to observe from a dark location. Avoid direct light from street lights and other sources. If possible observe from a dark location away from the light pollution that surrounds many of today's large cities.

You will see more stars after your eyes adapt to the darkness—usually about 10 to 20 minutes after you go outside. Also, if you need to use a torch to view the sky map, cover the light bulb with red cellophane. This will preserve your dark vision.

Finally, even though the Moon is one of the most stunning objects to view through a telescope, its light is so bright that it brightens the sky and makes many of the fainter objects very difficult to see. So try to observe the evening sky on moonless nights around either New Moon or Last Quarter.

Astronomical Glossary

Conjunction – An alignment of two celestial bodies such that they present the least angular separation as viewed from Earth.

Constellation – A defined area of the sky containing a star pattern.

Diffuse Nebula – A cloud of gas illuminated by nearby stars.

Double Star – Two stars that appear close to each other in the sky; either linked by gravity so that they orbit each other (binary star) or lying at different distances from Earth (optical double). Apparent separation of stars is given in seconds of arc (").

Ecliptic – The path of the Sun's center on the celestial sphere as seen from Earth.

Elongation – The angular separation of two celestial bodies. For Mercury and Venus the greatest elongation occurs when they are at their most angular distance from the Sun as viewed from Earth.

Galaxy – A mass of up to several billion stars held together by gravity.

Globular Star Cluster – A ball-shaped group of several thousand old stars.

Light Year (ly) – The distance a beam of light travels at 300,000 km/sec in one year.

Magnitude – The brightness of a celestial object as it appears in the sky.

Open Star Cluster – A group of tens or hundreds of relatively young stars.

Opposition – When a celestial body is opposite the Sun in the sky.

Planetary Nebula – The remnants of a shell of gas blown off by a star.

Universal Time (UT) – A time system used by astronomers. Also known as Greenwich Mean Time. USA Eastern Standard Time (for example, New York) is 5 hours behind UT.

Variable Star – A star that changes brightness over a period of time.

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE
DECEMBER 2025

CELESTIAL OBJECTS
Sky maps.com

Easily Seen with the Naked Eye

- | | | |
|------------|-----|---|
| Altair | Aql | • Brightest star in Aquila. Name means "the flying eagle". Dist=16.7 ly. |
| Capella | Aur | • The 6th brightest star. Appears yellowish in color. Spectroscopic binary. Dist=42 ly. |
| δ Cephei | Cep | • Cepheid prototype. Mag varies between 3.5 & 4.4 over 5.366 days. Mag 6 companion. |
| Deneb | Cyg | • Brightest star in Cygnus. One of the greatest known supergiants. Dist=1,400±200 ly. |
| Castor | Gem | • Multiple star system with 6 components. 3 stars visible in telescope. Dist=52 ly. |
| Pollux | Gem | • With Castor, the twin sons of Leda in classical mythology. Dist=34 ly. |
| Vega | Lyr | • The 5th brightest star in the sky. A blue-white star. Dist=25.0 ly. |
| Rigel | Ori | • The brightest star in Orion. Blue supergiant star with mag 7 companion. Dist=770 ly. |
| Betelgeuse | Ori | • One of the largest red supergiant stars known. Diameter=300 times that of Sun. Dist=430 ly. |
| Algot | Per | • Famous eclipsing binary star. Magnitude varies between 2.1 & 3.4 over 2.867 days. |
| Fomalhaut | PsA | • Brightest star in Piscis Austrinus. In Arabic the "fish's mouth". Dist=25 ly. |
| Pleiades | Tau | • The Seven Sisters. Spectacular cluster. Many more stars visible in binoculars. Dist=399 ly. |
| Hyades | Tau | • Large V-shaped star cluster. Binoculars reveal many more stars. Dist=152 ly. |
| Aldebaran | Tau | • Brightest star in Taurus. It is not associated with the Hyades star cluster. Dist=65 ly. |
| Polaris | UMi | • The North Pole Star. A telescope reveals an unrelated mag 8 companion star. Dist=433 ly. |

Easily Seen with Binoculars

- | | | |
|----------------|-----|---|
| M31 | And | • The Andromeda Galaxy. Most distant object visible to naked eye. Dist=2.5 million ly. |
| M2 | Aqr | • Resembles a fuzzy star in binoculars. |
| η Aquilae | Aql | • Bright Cepheid variable. Mag varies between 3.6 & 4.5 over 7.166 days. Dist=1,200 ly. |
| M38 | Aur | • Stars appear arranged in "pi" or cross shape. Dist=4,300 ly. |
| M36 | Aur | • About half size of M38. Located in rich Milky Way star field. Dist=4,100 ly. |
| M37 | Aur | • Very fine star cluster. Discovered by Messier in 1764. Dist=4,400 ly. |
| μ Cephei | Cep | • Herschel's Garnet Star. One of the reddest stars. Mag 3.4 to 5.1 over 730 days. |
| Mira | Cet | • Famous long period variable star. Mag varies between 3.0 & 10.1 over 332 days. |
| χ Cygni | Cyg | • Long period pulsating red giant. Magnitude varies between 3.3 & 14.2 over 407 days. |
| M39 | Dra | • May be visible to the naked eye under good conditions. Dist=900 ly. |
| ν Draconis | Dra | • Wide pair of white stars. One of the finest binocular pairs in the sky. Dist=100 ly. |
| M35 | Gem | • Fine open cluster located near foot of the twin Castor. Dist=2,800 ly. |
| M92 | Her | • Fainter and smaller than M13. Use a telescope to resolve its stars. |
| ε Lyrae | Lyr | • Famous Double Double. Binoculars show a double star. High power reveals each a double. |
| β Lyrae | Lyr | • Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.9 & 5.0 over 46.0 days. |
| Cr 69 | Ori | • Lambda Orionis Cluster. Dist=1,630 ly. |
| M42 | Ori | • The Great Orion Nebula. Spectacular bright nebula. Best in telescope. Dist=1,300 light years. |
| M15 | Peg | • Only globular known to contain a planetary nebula (Mag 14, d=1"). Dist=30,000 ly. |
| Double Cluster | Per | • Double Cluster in Perseus. NGC 869 & 884. Excellent in binoculars. Dist=7,300 ly. |
| 253 | ScI | • Fine, large, cigar-shaped galaxy. Requires dark sky. Member of Sculptor Group. |
| Cr 399 | Vul | • Coathanger asterism or "Brocchi's Cluster". Not a true star cluster. Dist=218 to 1,140 ly. |

Telescopic Objects

- | | | |
|---------------|-----|--|
| γ Andromedae | And | • Attractive double star. Bright orange star with mag 5 blue companion. Sep=9.8". |
| 7009 | Aqr | • Saturn Nebula. Requires 8-inch telescope to see Saturn-like appendages. |
| 7293 | Aqr | • Helix Nebula. Spans nearly 1/4 deg. Requires dark sky. Dist=300 ly. |
| γ Arietis | Ari | • Impressive looking double blue-white star. Visible in a small telescope. Sep=7.8". |
| η Cassiopeiae | Cas | • Yellow star mag 3.4 & orange star mag 7.5. Dist=19 ly. Orbit=480 years. Sep=12". |
| Albireo | Cyg | • Beautiful double star. Contrasting colours of orange and blue-green. Sep=34.4". |
| 61 Cygni | Cyg | • Attractive double star. Mags 5.2 & 6.1 orange dwarfs. Dist=11.4 ly. Sep=28.4". |
| γ Delphini | Del | • Appear yellow & white. Mags 4.2 & 5.2. Dist=100 ly. Struve 2725 double in same field. |
| ε Eridani | Eri | • Striking blue-white double star. Mags 3.2 & 4.3. Visible in a small telescope. Sep=8.2". |
| β Lyrae | Lyr | • Eclipsing binary. Mag varies between 3.3 & 4.3 over 12.940 days. Fainter mag 7.2 blue star. |
| M57 | Lyr | • Ring Nebula. Magnificent object. Smoke-ring shape. Dist=4,100 ly. |
| α Orionis | Ori | • Superb multiple star. 2 mag 7 stars one side, mag 9 star on other. Struve 761 triple in field. |
| M1 | Tau | • Crab Nebula. Remnant from supernova which was visible in 1054. Dist=6,500 ly. |
| M33 | Tri | • Fine face-on spiral galaxy. Requires a large aperture telescope. Dist=2.3 million ly. |
| M81 | UMa | • Beautiful spiral galaxy visible with binoculars. Easy to see in a telescope. |
| M82 | UMa | • Close to M81 but much fainter and smaller. |
| M27 | Vul | • Dumbbell Nebula. Large, twin-lobed shape. Most spectacular planetary. Dist=975 ly. |

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Astrophotography

Lunar Maria

- Noah Frere

Evening of Nov 6th at TAO
Meade 12" SCT (LX-200)
Canon t3 at prime focus:
ISO 100, 1/160 s
Edited with Affinity

Reflection Nebula IC 5076 in Cygnus

- Don Spong

Due to travel, I haven't done much astrophotography the last few weeks. The following image of the reflection nebula IC 5076 was made on November 3 using my Celestron Edge HD, ZWO AM5 mount, Hyperstar attachment, ZWO 533 MC pro camera, Williams optics guide scope, ZWO 220MM guide camera, all controlled by my ZWO ASI AIR. Around 17 30-second images were stacked and processed with PixInsight. IC 5076 is in the constellation Cygnus near the bright star Deneb. The stars surrounding it are part of NGC 6991, an open cluster.

IC 5076 – taken from TAO November 3

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc.
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}$ (Barnes's rule ☺).

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C(c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_2$ (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) = S_1 S_2 + C_1 C_2 c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas @ 1 kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$\text{Image scale [asec/px]} = 206.3 * \text{pixel size}[\mu\text{m}] / \text{focal length [mm]}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, with errors (from Gaia data, or Simbad if needed as an alternative).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.0054	41	Menkalinan	81.1	0.46
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6	7.0
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.0083	43	Alhena	109.3	8.2
4	Arcturus	36.72	0.22	44	Peacock	178.8	5.1
5	Vega	25.04	0.069	45	Alsephina	80.6	0.78
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7	16.4
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6	6.3
8	Procyon	11.46	0.051	48	Alphard	180.3	1.8
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8	0.33
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3	0.46
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	81.1	0.93
12	Altair	16.73	0.049	52	Nunki	227.8	4.6
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8	0.21
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0	1.01
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4	6.7
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6	0.77
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1	2.7
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9	0.63
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	974.	37.
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9	0.21
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	89.9	3.47
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0	4.0
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2	1.5
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6	18.0
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5	10.0
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	77.2	1.79
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5	85.
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1830	270
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3	0.7
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	231.5	8.2
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1080	40
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0	49.
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7	0.35
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.9	8.4
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6	11.
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5	27.
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2	66.
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7	0.27
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7	6.0
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	84.5	2.5

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		Θ	$\Delta\theta$	defect (%)
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

What is the late November doing
With the disturbance of the spring
And creatures of the summer heat,
And snowdrops writhing under feet
And hollyhocks that aim too high
Red into grey and tumble down
Late roses filled with early snow?

Thunder rolled by the rolling stars
Simulates triumphal cars
Deployed in constellated wars
Scorpion fights against the Sun
Until the Sun and Moon go down
Comets weep and Leonids fly
Hunt the heavens and the plains
Whirled in a vortex that shall bring
The world to that destructive fire
Which burns before the ice-cap reigns.

T.S. Eliot
from *East Coker*
in "Four Quartets," (1940)

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO? (Bortle 5.0)

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

Gdome = N 35° 49' 56.6", W 84° 37' 03.8"; Alt. 322 m

NE Pad = N 35° 49' 57.4", W 84° 37' 03.1"; Alt. 322 m

Where is Obed?

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

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Vol. 50, Issue 09, Fri 13 Sep 2024:	13742825
Vol. 50, Issue 10, Fri 11 Oct 2024:	13921735
Vol. 50, Issue 11, Fri 15 Nov 2024:	14171218
Vol. 50, Issue 12, Fri 13 Dec 2024:	14394899
Vol. 51, Issue 01, Fri 10 Jan 2025:	14630165
Vol. 51, Issue 02, Fri 14 Feb 2025:	14873015
Vol. 51, Issue 03, Fri 14 Mar 2025:	15015954
Vol. 51, Issue 04, Fri 11 Apr 2025:	15200349
Vol. 51, Issue 05, Fri 16 May 2025:	15443035
Vol. 51, Issue 06, Fri 13 Jun 2025:	15660329
Vol. 51, Issue 07, Fri 11 Jul 2025:	15865574

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Vol. 51, Issue 12; Fri 12 Dec 2025:	17873056

A generic link that lists Trapezium pdf issues (and other ORION documents) starting with the most recent, which does not require a specific zenodo document number, follows:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rigel/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Fin du journal

December 2025